

COMPARISON OF TREADMILL AND TRACK BASED WALKING ON CARDIOPULMONARY FITNESS IN UNDERGRADUATE HEALTHY STUDENTS

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Abstract

Objective: The main objective of this research was to compare the effect of treadmill-based and track based walking training on cardiopulmonary fitness in University Students of Faisalabad.

Methodology: A Shuttle Run Test which is commonly used in sports settings and health centers to assess the cardiopulmonary fitness was used in this research study. The data was collected from the 98 participants of College of Physical Therapy and Department of sports sciences, GC University Faisalabad and it took around 9 months to complete this study.

Results: Mann-Whitney test and the *p*-value of .000 shows there is a significant difference between group comparisons of VO₂ Max. Grouping Variable was set as those who used treadmill and those who used track-based walking to achieve better cardiopulmonary fitness. Data showed the difference between the VO₂ Max of different weeks, and the *p*-value indicates that there is a significant difference between all these variables. There is also a difference of mean between these 3 pairs.

Conclusion: The study concluded that there is a significant difference found between VO₂ Max of the participants throughout the course of 12 weeks. In addition to that it was also found that there is a significant difference between the VO₂ Max of participants who used different cardiopulmonary fitness techniques like treadmill walking and track based walking. For those participants who were using track-based walking showed higher values of the VO₂ Max than treadmill walkers. Moreover, between groups analysis also shows the difference between VO₂ Max of the participants. And there was a significant correlation present between all the groups.

INTRODUCTION

Cardiopulmonary fitness (CPF) is a component of health-related physical fitness that provide the inhalational oxygen to the muscles that are exercising.

Death due to heart disease decreases due to cardiopulmonary fitness. Lower mortality is linked to increased fitness. In cardiopulmonary fitness the main

indicative component is maximum oxygen uptake (VO_2 max).(1) More VO_2 max the more person will be physical fit. Physical activity is related to the physical fitness. Physical fitness is defined as the ability to do work of daily activities with a great energy and without fatigue.

In 2020 world health organization updated their guidelines in which they stated that physical activity is better for good health. Physical activity make the men the fit that decreases their risk of death.(2)

Use of treadmill is more beneficial to assess the cardiopulmonary fitness of the students. Different studies have been conducted to assess the effect of treadmill training and over ground walking for VO_2 max.(3) But there were the controversies present between the treadmill and over ground walking. Some studies showed the similar effect of both walking and some studies showed the different results.(4)

In 2018, one study was conducted to compare the effects of low intensity treadmill training and high intensity treadmill training to assess the cardiorespiratory fitness, gait ability and the quality of life of the stroke patients. And their results showed that high intensity treadmill training is much better to improve the gait ability and it also increases VO_2 max.(5)

In 2020, another study was conducted to compare the effect of land walking and water walking on fitness. But their results showed the similarity index that land walking and water walking has the same effect on the fitness.(6)

Assessments of cardiorespiratory fitness in terms of (VO_2 max) have a lot of potential for public health monitoring in terms of predicting future health, early retirement, and ability to live independently.(7) The goal of this study was to create a VO_2 max prediction model using the results of the 6MWT in healthy adults. Their result showed that 6MWT on a 15-meter track is a reliable field test for predicting VO_2 max in healthy adults with a 1MET accuracy.(8)

As a result, we will compare the effects of treadmill-based training (MT) versus track-based training (TT) on cardiopulmonary fitness over a 12-week period. So that was gap found after reviewing the different literature. So, in the current study we will compare the results of both studies.(9)

Treadmill is considered to be advantageous in locomotion research as it allows a controlled and suitable environment for testing and then training for the patients. It allows the movement within a small area and monitors can be attached to visualize the gait. A wide range of comparison studies have been conducted to compare the kinetics of walk during treadmill and track walking.(10)

Parvataneni et al. concluded that more energy is consumed in treadmill walk with the same speed as in track based walk.(11) Cinematography has made it much easier to compare the similarities and differences in performing human skills.(12)

A key focus of physical activity promotion is walk and cycling, however, its general effect on health and all-cause mortality is still not clear. Most of the studies focus on physical activity in overall and leisure time. But less consideration has been given to walking and cycling.(13) Considering kinematics, studies show inconsistent evidence on similarity of treadmill (TW) and over ground walking (OW) and compare TW and OW. Elliot and Blanks by reported that an increased stride rate and decreased time in wing is a result of decreased stride length in treadmill runners.(14)

The cardiopulmonary fitness of a person defines how well an individual can sustain during the regular activities of life. Individuals with better fitness levels can bear high oxygen demands efficiently as compared to the people with average fitness level. The current study aims to compare the effect of treadmill training and track based walking training on the cardiopulmonary fitness of the University students.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Design:

It was a Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT).

Study Setting:

The data was collected from the College of Physical Therapy and Department of sports sciences, GC University Faisalabad

Duration of study:

9 months to complete this study.

Sample size:

The sample size of 98 was calculated by using this formula

$$n = \frac{2\sigma^2(z_{1-\alpha/2} + z_{1-\beta})^2}{(\mu_1 - \mu_2)^2}$$

Sampling technique:

Convenient sampling technique was used to collect the data from the participants

Sample selection

Inclusion criteria:

- Students of Government College University Faisalabad
- Subjects between 20-30 years of age
- Both genders

Exclusion criteria:

- Subjects with Neurological disorders
- Subjects with Musculoskeletal disorders

Equipment:

- Flat, non-slip surface
- Marker cones
- Measurement tape
- Stopwatch
- Treadmill

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE:

After the ethical approval from the research committee a Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT) was conducted for comparison of treadmill and track based walking on cardiopulmonary fitness in undergraduate healthy students. A Shuttle Run Test which is commonly used in sports settings and health centers to assess the cardiopulmonary fitness was used in this research study. This test comprises of running movements which are back and forth either over the changing distance or with the same distance. This test was used to assess the attributes which are linked to physiological properties, from short duration high intensity tests which measured agility and speed to the longer and slower paced tests which measure the

aerobic fitness, and all of this was depending on the intensity, distance and duration of the test.

The major equipment which was used for to perform this test was marker cones, stopwatch, and shuttle run CD, CD player, Measurement tape and non-slip surface. Every participant was asked to undergo through this procedure and the data was recorded by the assessors. At start participant was standing behind the starting line and when the person hears the sound beep on the CD player he started running back and forth at a particular pace or as quickly as possible between a set distance until the participant was unable to continue.

The data was collected from the 98 participants of College of Physical Therapy and Department of sports sciences, GC University Faisalabad and it took around 9 months to complete this study after the approval of synopsis. Students who met the inclusion criteria were included in this study and the ones who were not meeting the inclusion criteria were excluded from this study. A Consent form was given to the participants which was signed by all the participants and their credentials were kept secret from everyone.

RESULTS

The participant's weight was a very important factor in this study and this table shows majority of the participants who participated in this study were between ranged between the ages of 67-75. The participants smoking history was a very important factor in this study because this can alter or hinder in achieving cardiopulmonary fitness and majority (74.5%) of the participants who participated in this study were non-smokers.

Table 2 shows the frequency of those participants who regularly exercise even before the start of this study. 74.5 % of the participants said they were not much

active nor they did any kind of exercise. Similarly, 25.5 % of the participants said they were doing their exercises on daily basis. Normality of the data was assessed with the help of Kolmogorov Smirnov test the data distribution of the participants and the p-value of .000 shows the data was not normally distributed.

Table 3 for pair 1 Week 0 VO₂ Max mean and standard deviation 25.130±7.3253 at week 4 VO₂ Max mean and standard deviation was 36.510±6.5439 there was a significant difference in mean of VO₂ Max. Pair 2 shows that Week 0 VO₂ Max mean was 25.130±7.3253 and after intervention mean at Week 8 was VO₂ Max 58.044±3.8125 which was also significant. Pair 3 shows that at Week 12 VO₂ Max mean was 68.417±4.5045.

Table 4 shows the statistics of the Mann-Whitney test and the p-value of .000 shows there is a significant difference between group comparisons of VO₂ Max. Grouping Variable was set as those who used treadmill and those who used track-based walking to achieve better cardiopulmonary fitness, Data showed the difference between the VO₂ Max of different weeks, and the p-value indicates that there is a significant difference between all these variables. There is also a difference of mean between these 3 pairs. ANOVA test was applied to see the VO₂ max in both treatment groups during course of follow up time duration (baseline till 12th week). And the p-value indicates there is significant change during the course of follow up.

DISCUSSION

Cardiopulmonary fitness is defined as the ability that provide the energy for physical activity and to eliminate the fatigue elements after providing the fuel. CPF is often expressed in metabolic equivalents (METs), maximal oxygen consumption (VO₂max), the volume of O₂ consumed in 1 kilogramme of body weight during 1 minute, ml/kg/min), or the endurance time in an activity test. The rate at which the body consumes and transport the oxygen is called the oxygen uptake (VO₂). Oxygen uptake is measured usually during the graded exercise program, when oxygen uptake is recorded as highest during the exercise it is called maximum oxygen uptake (VO₂ max). When we evaluate the endurance and aerobic fitness of the person then we accurately measure the

VO₂ max.(15) The most important test for evaluating the VO₂ max is graded treadmill test. This test measures the exercise capacity.(16) The greater the value of VO₂ max then greater will be the cardiopulmonary fitness. So the main aim of our study was to determine the effect of treadmill based and track based training on cardiopulmonary fitness.

In our study the mean age was calculated 24.24±1.916, and the other three variables such as height, weight and body mass index were calculated and their mean values were 5.57±0.166, 70.71±2.87 and 25.32±1.37 respectively. Another study in 2017 was conducted and their variable such as age was in between 18-26 years and their body mass index was ≥26kg\m.(17)

Baseline data showed that there is a visibly marked difference found between VO₂ Max of the participant's throughout the course of 12 weeks. In addition to that it was also found that there is a significant difference between the VO₂ Max of participants who used different cardiopulmonary fitness techniques like treadmill walking and track based walking.(18)

In 2015, one study was conducted to compare the effect of high load and low load resistance training program on the endurance and hypertrophy of the muscles.(19) And their results at the end of the study showed that high load training had a major role to increase the endurance of the muscles and the hypertrophy of the muscles.(20)

In the current study the response of the participants showed that they regularly exercise even before the start of this study. 74.5 % of the participants said they were not much active nor they did any kind of exercise. Similarly, 25.5 % of the participants said they were doing their exercises on daily basis.

According to our survey, the different technique that was used by the participants during the study to achieve cardiopulmonary fitness were equally distributed into two groups. 50% of the participants used treadmill and 50% of the participants use track based walking technique for cardiopulmonary fitness.(21)

The data of VO₂max was calculated from week 0 to week 12. The results showed that the correlation between the VO₂ Max of different weeks and the p-value indicates that there is a significant correlation between all these variables as shown in the above

table.(22) In asthma and 18 year old children the effectiveness and safety of swimming exercise training was checked. Swimming exercise improves lung function (moderate strength evidence) and cardiopulmonary fitness in children and adolescents with stable asthma, according to his review (high strength evidence). Swimming training did not appear to have any negative impact on asthma control in young persons aged 18 and under who had stable asthma of any severity. This review, however, cannot tell whether swimming is superior then other forms of physical activity. To better assess the long-term advantages of swimming, more appropriately powered trials with longer follow-up periods are required.(23) And the result of our study showed that the difference between the VO2 Max of different weeks and the p-value indicates that there is a significant difference between all these variables. There is also a difference of mean between these 3 pairs.

The p-value of .000 shows there is a significant difference between group comparisons of VO2 Max. Grouping variable was set as those who used treadmill and those who used track based walking to achieve better cardiopulmonary fitness. Another study was conducted on eight track athletes, treadmill and track running comparisons were made. Maximum aerobic power (VO2 max) and oxygen intake (VO2) were assessed in a distinct series of three speeds and at maximal effort. From slowest to fastest, the running speeds were always in order. And their results showed that there were several correlations:

VO2 max with body weight ($r = .83$, P less than .02), VO2 max determinations on the treadmill and track ($r = .95$, P less than .01), and 3) VO2 ml/kg with running velocity m/min ($r = .91$, P less than .01), where the regression was linear and may be represented by the equation $Y = 5.36 + 0.172X$, where $S_{yx} = 2.7$ m102/kg The conclusion is that treadmill measurements of oxygen uptake can be used to track running in calm air at speeds ranging from 180 to 260 m/min.(24) The goal of this study was to see how interval and continuous running affected parameters related to cardiovascular health.(25)

Current study highlighted that there is a significant difference found between VO2 Max of the participants throughout the course of 12 weeks. In addition to that it was also found that there is a significant difference between the VO2 Max of

participants who used different cardiopulmonary fitness techniques like treadmill walking and track based walking. For those participants who were using track-based walking showed higher values of the VO2 Max than treadmill walkers. Moreover, between groups analysis also shows the difference between VO2 Max of the participants. And there was a significant correlation present between all the groups.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that there is a significant difference found between VO2 Max of the participants throughout the course of 12 weeks. Moreover, between groups analysis also shows the difference between VO2 Max of the participants. And there was a significant correlation present between all the groups.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

This is a demand to investigate these factors more precisely which includes application of different test to find out the results. In addition to this, it should be done on a larger sample size which could represent the whole country or at least a whole province. Different other factors like in exercising in different environments and the speed of the walking should also be measured to make the results more accurate. Further evaluation is also needed especially in people of all ages with a larger sample size.

LIMITATIONS:

First limitation regarding this study was the population, which was selected from only certain age and from only one city of Pakistan and it does not represent the other cities, whole district or the country. The second limitation was we were not able to use the random sampling technique for data collection because the majority of the college and universities were closed due to the pandemic and summer break. The third limitation was regarding the small sample size which happened to be around 92 participants and it does not represent the every class and every kind of student of Pakistan. Another limitation was that this study was conducted only on the students.

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Tables

Table 1: Participants characteristics

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	98	22	27	24.24	1.916
Height	98	5.3	5.7	5.577	.1636
Weight	98	67	75	70.71	2.872
BMI	98	23.7	27.3	25.324	1.3795

Table 2: Participants who Perform Exercise

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Yes	25	25.5
	No	73	74.5
	Total	98	100.0

Table 3: Difference of samples between different weeks

Paired Samples Test									
		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Week 0 VO2 Max - Week 4 VO2 Max	-11.3806	1.5136	.1529	-11.6841	-11.0772	-74.435	97	.000
Pair 2	Week 0 VO2 Max - Week 8 VO2 Max	-32.9143	4.0263	.4067	-33.7215	-32.1071	-80.926	97	.000

Pair 3	Week 0 VO2 Max - Week 12 VO2 Max	- 43.2878	3.2282	.3261	-43.9350	-42.6405	- 132.743	97	.000
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Table 4: Mann-Whitney test Statics

	Test Statistics			
	Week 0 VO2 Max	Week 4 VO2 Max	Week 8 VO2 Max	Week 12 VO2 Max
Mann-Whitney U	.000	.000	288.000	.000
Wilcoxon W	1225.000	1225.000	1513.000	1225.000
Z	-9.286	-8.809	-7.035	-9.286
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000
a. Grouping Variable: Technique Used for Cardiopulmonary Fitness				

